

Study on the Thermal Decomposition of Ammonium Nitrate Using Mass Spectrometric Technique

S. K. ADHYA, S. K. MUKHERJEE and B. K. BANERJEE

Research & Development, The Fertilizer (P & D) India Ltd., P.O. Sindri-828 122,
Dhanbad (Bihar), India

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Thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrate in the temperature range 40 to 200° under reduced pressure (10^{-6} – 10^{-4} torr) with continuous removal of the evolved gases has been carried out with the help of a mass spectrometer. The analysis of evolved gases at different stages of temperature reveals that the decomposition process is strongly temperature dependent and follows three distinct paths in the three different temperature ranges which are briefly represented as follows :

Measurements of ion intensity ratios against temperatures supports these findings.

AMMONIUM nitrate exhibits a tendency to decompose on keeping due to thermal effects and interaction with the environment. This encouraged numerous workers to study its thermal decomposition mechanism^{1,6,9,10,16,20,22,25,30}. Several attempts have also been made to determine the composition of evolved gas mixture^{9,15,25,28}, effects of various additives^{3,18,22} and determination of rate constants^{2,7,9,14,25,26,30}. Various physical techniques like mass spectrometry^{8,29} and gas chromatography⁴ have also been applied to assist such studies from time to time.

In 1954, Feick and Hainer¹¹ suggested that at 170°, NH₃ and HNO₃ were formed first followed by the formation of N₂O and H₂O at 290°. Later on in 1968, Heinrich¹³ contradicted Feick's findings and reported that the initial formation was N₂O and H₂O, whereas NH₃ and HNO₃ were formed at the second stage. Party *et al.*²⁰ detected hydrazine in the reaction products between NH₃ and NO₂ upto 100° whereas Guiochon¹² found the intermediate formation of NH₂NO₂ species in the above decomposition process. In early seventies Manclis¹⁷ critically reviewed its decomposition process. Later on in 1975 Biskupski and Kotackowski⁵ did further work in the line.

In the present investigation the decomposition of ammonium nitrate has been studied inside the mass spectrometer source chamber where high vacuum (10^{-6} torr) is maintained constantly. This technique facilitates the immediate detection of any intermediate or transient species formed as the possibility of gas phase interaction is automatically minimized and will help in understanding the decomposition mechanism of ammonium nitrate.

Experimental

Ammonium nitrate sample used in this experiment was of AnalaR variety. Aqueous solution of the sample was taken in the glass capillary sample tube and dried in a desiccator. The dried sample was then introduced in the mass spectrometer through the solid introduction probe. The spectra were recorded from 40 to 140° with 20° interval and at 170° and 200° also, setting the mass scanning range from m/e 12 to 100. High resolution, high speed analysis was carried out for the detailed analysis of individual mass peaks at m/e 17, 18, 30, 44, 46 and 63.

The ion intensity ratio values are shown in Table 1.

The apparatus used in this study was a double focussing double beam MS30DB mass spectrometer, supplied by M/s. AEI England, operated under the following conditions :

Nature of Ionization	: Electron Impact
Electron volts	: 70 e. v.
Electron current	: 300 μ A
Accelerating Voltage	: 4 KV
Scan Speed	: 30 sec/Dec
Resolution	: 1000 & 3000
Sensitivity	: 6.0
Source Temperature	: 60-220°
Reference Material	: Perfluoro Kerosine.
Recording	: U. V. Oscillographic

TABLE 1—PEAK INTENSITY RATIOS OF DIFFERENT IONS OF NH₄NO₃ AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

TEMPERATURE	INTENSITY RATIO OF					
	(NO ⁺ 30/46 (NO ⁺) ₂)	(NH ₃ ⁺)17/69(HNO ₃ ⁺)	(N ₂ O ⁺)17/63(HNO ₃ ⁺)	(NO ⁺)44/63(HNO ₃ ⁺)	(N ₂ O ⁺)44/46(NO ₂ ⁺)	
40	0.637	—	—	—	—	—
60	0.617	40.0	0.1	3.2	0.144	
80	0.627	40.9	0.342	6.0	0.141	
100	0.611	45.0	0.428	6.0	0.166	
120	0.622	—	0.416	6.25	0.196	
140	0.603	41.66	3.0	20.0	0.190	
170	8.0	—	2.909	—	40.0	
200	13.33	—	0.555	—	8.33	

Results and Discussion

The absence of parent peak (m/e 80) in the temperature range 40-200° indicates the unstability of ammonium nitrate both thermally and under electron impact. Among the few peaks observed in the spectra at 40°, m/e 17 is found to be double natured and shows the presence of both NH₃⁺ and OH⁺ ions in which the intensity of NH₃⁺ ion is more. The peak at m/e 30 and m/e 46 are confirmed to be due to NO⁺ and NO₂⁺ respectively which are formed in the following way :

The formation of NO⁺ ion may also be due to fragmentation of NO₂⁺ under electron impact. The peak due to HNO₃⁺ (m/e 63) appears at 60° and persists prominently upto 140°. Upto this temperature range it is found that the variation in the ratios of NH₃⁺/HNO₃⁺ is nearly constant (Fig. 1) which clearly indicates that NH₃⁺ and HNO₃ formation is the product of the same reaction and is designated as the first path (Path A) of thermal decomposition of NH₄NO₃ which is also reported earlier^{21,23}. The weak intensity of m/e 63 peak with respect to NH₃⁺ peak reveals the relative unstability of HNO₃⁺ under the experimental condition. After 140° the peak at m/e 17 is due to OH₂⁺ ion only as confirmed from its singlet nature.

The spectra in the temperature region 170-200° shows the presence of intense peaks of H₂O⁺m/e 18, OH⁺ at m/e 17 and not due to NH₃⁺ as is evident from its singlet nature and a peak at m/e 44 due to N₂O⁺ ion as confirmed by fast scanning and high resolution settings (Fig. 2).

The ion intensity ratio of (N₂O₁₇⁺/H₂O₁₈⁺) at different temperatures (Fig. 1) is found to be constant in the temperature range 140 to 170° which confirms that these fragments are the results of the following reaction

which is considered as the second decomposition

path, (path B). The spectra at 200° shows major peaks at m/e 18 due to H₂O⁺ (base peak), m/e 30 due to NO⁺ and an abrupt reduction in the intensity of m/e 44 peak. It is therefore, concluded that at higher temperature NH₄NO₃ produces NO and H₂O as the ultimate product.

A weak but very persistent peak at m/e 64 which is confirmed to be due to NH₄NO₂ ion is found to be present from 60 to 200° which has probably formed due to electronic fragmentation of NH₄NO₃. According to P. Ray *et al.*¹⁹ NH₄NO₂ once formed can be sublimed undecomposed under reduced pressure upto 60°. As the vacuum order in the present experimental condition is very high (approx 8 × 10⁻⁶ to 9 × 10⁻⁷ torr) it is very much probable that NH₄NO₂ formed remained undecomposed even upto 200°.

A better understanding of the results and important features of the different species formed is obtained by plotting the ion intensity ratios against temperature. As stated earlier the ratio of NH₃⁺/HNO₃⁺ (Fig. 1a) is practically constant suggesting their interrelated formation. In a similar way the ratio of N₂O⁺/H₂O⁺ (Fig. 1b) is constant in the

Fig. 1. Relative ion intensity vs temperature curves of (a) NH₃⁺/HNO₃⁺, (b) N₂O⁺/H₂O⁺, (c) N₂O⁺/HNO₃⁺, (d) N₂O⁺/NO₂⁺, (e) NO⁺/NO₂⁺.

temperature range 140 to 170° indicating that reaction (B) takes place in this range. A sudden fall in

the ratio value of N_2O^+/H_2O^+ above 170° and upto 200° shows that after 170° either N_2O formation decreases or H_2O formation increases. The spectra gives a clear indication that with increase of temperature N_2O formation decreases. This is further supported by an increase in the ratio value of NO^+/NO_2^+ after 170° and a sudden fall in the ratio of N_2O^+/NO_2^+ after 170° (Fig. 1d). Below 140° , the lower portion of the ratio plot of N_2O^+/H_2O^+ (Fig. 1b) indicates that initially either some moisture was present in the sample, or water is formed as a result of chemical interaction amongst the decomposition products of NH_4NO_3 as indicated below.

which is slowly lost with the further increase of temperature and ceases after 120° .

The constant ratio values of NO^+/NO_2^+ (Fig. 1e) in the temperature range $40-140^\circ$ show that NO^+ is

formed totally from NO_2^+ by electronic impact. Above 140° a steep rise in the curve indicates that NO^+ is also formed from NH_4NO_3 by thermal decomposition. The ratio value of N_2O^+/NO_2^+ (Fig. 2) is approximately constant upto 140° having a maximum at 170° , confirming its maximum formation there. After 170° N_2O^+/NO_2^+ ratio again falls down showing reduction in N_2O^+ formation at higher temperatures.

The experimental results show that the thermal decomposition of NH_4NO_3 is strongly temperature dependent. With variation of temperature it follows three different decomposition routes namely (A), (B) and (C). The reactions (A) and (B) occur simultaneously with ceasing of reaction (A) after certain temperature, where reaction (B) become more prominent. At still higher temperatures the decomposition follows path (C). The variation in the reaction temperatures as observed is attributed to be due to the high vacuum prevailed during the experiment.

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Fig. 2. High speed and high resolution mass spectra of M/E 63, 46, 44, 30 at different temperatures.

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